

BRIDGING THE GAP IN TYPE 2 DIABETES CARE: EXPLORING KEY BARRIERS AND SUPPORTIVE FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

A chronic metabolic disease marked by high blood glucose levels; diabetes mellitus can cause major complications that impact multiple organs. It is becoming more commonplace worldwide, with India being particularly affected. This study measures medication adherence, examines the factors that influence glycemic control in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), and assesses quality of life. 248 patients with type 2 diabetes participated in a prospective study at Sagar Hospitals in Bengaluru. The revised Diabetes Quality of Life (DQOL) instrument, the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Scale (HB-MAS), and self-designed forms were used to gather data. SPSS version 20 was used for statistical analyses. According to the study, 54.4% of participants were over 60, and 46.4% of participants were male. A sizeable percentage (87.5%) was 60.5% had unhealthy eating habits, and 60.5% were not physically active. Over time, there was an improvement in glucose control, with low medication adherence decreasing from 37.0% to 2.01% and good HbA1c control rising from 16.5% to 21.7%. Poor quality of life dropped from 55.6% to 3.7%, indicating a noticeable improvement in quality-of-life scores. The results highlight the necessity of addressing glycemic control obstacles and improving medication adherence via patient education and lifestyle changes. Our responsibilities as clinical pharmacists include encouraging adherence, offering guidance, and assisting with lifestyle modifications. The study's findings guide diabetes community programs, aid in the development of public health policies, and enhance medication and patient compliance, all of which contribute to the reduction of complications and improvement of T2DM patients' quality of life.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2 Diabetes, Glycemic Control, Medication Adherence, Quality of Life

1. INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a long-term metabolic disease marked by persistently high blood sugar levels brought on by deficiencies in either the action or secretion of insulin, or both. Because of insulin's crucial anabolic role in controlling blood glucose, it profoundly changes how proteins, fats, and carbohydrates are metabolised. The most common characteristic of diabetes, a diverse group of metabolic diseases, is persistently high blood sugar levels resulting from either decreased insulin secretion or insulin resistance.¹

Diabetes can be broadly classified into four major types based on its pathogenesis and clinical features: type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM), type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), and other specific forms of diabetes.² A lifelong reliance on insulin therapy and complete insulin insufficiency are the outcomes of T1DM, which is more prevalent in children and adolescents and is caused by the autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells. Rare forms, like fulminant and idiopathic T1DM, can develop suddenly or without autoimmune symptoms.¹ Insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency are the causes of type 2 diabetes, which is the most common type worldwide. Due to fast urbanisation and lifestyle changes, it is increasingly being diagnosed in younger age groups and is strongly associated with obesity, sedentary lifestyles, and unhealthy diets.³ Pregnancy-induced GDM typically goes away after delivery, but it raises the mother's chance of getting type 2 diabetes in the future. Other distinct forms include endocrinopathies, exocrine pancreatic disorders, monogenic diabetes syndromes, and diabetes brought on by drugs or chemicals.²

Diabetes cases have dramatically increased in India, known as the diabetes capital of the world, from 33 million in 2000 to 72 million in 2021, with estimates of 125 million by 2045.¹ Urbanisation, a decline in physical activity, population growth, and a genetic predisposition that results in the "thin-fat" phenotype are all contributing factors. People with this distinct South Asian phenotype are more likely to develop insulin resistance earlier in life because they have higher visceral adiposity but less muscle mass.⁴ T2DM is becoming more prevalent due to early complications and decreased productivity, and the mean age of onset is alarmingly decreasing.⁴

Early-stage diabetes, particularly type 2 diabetes, can be clinically asymptomatic, delaying diagnosis. When polydipsia, polyuria, fatigue, blurred vision, inexplicable weight loss, slow-healing wounds, numbness or tingling in the extremities, and recurrent infections are present, these symptoms may be present.⁴ These symptoms develop into serious consequences like retinopathy, neuropathy, nephropathy, and cardiovascular disease if they are not identified and treated early.

A complex interaction between hormonal and metabolic dysfunctions is part of the underlying pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes. Increased hepatic glucose production, impaired insulin secretion, and peripheral tissue insulin resistance are examples of central mechanisms. Increased lipolysis, decreased incretin effect, increased glucagon secretion, neurotransmitter dysfunction, enhanced renal glucose reabsorption, and impaired glucose uptake in muscle and adipose tissue are some of the other factors that are described by the "ominous octet" framework.⁶ Collectively, these anomalies result in β -cell fatigue and persistent hyperglycemia, which prolongs the course of the illness.

A lot of T2DM patients still have trouble controlling their **blood sugar levels**, even with improvements in treatment options and clinical recommendations. Improving results requires

determining the complex obstacles to glycemic control. These include a lack of exercise, irregular blood sugar levels, poor eating habits, stress, and problems with medications.^{4,5} Thus, identifying these obstacles and comprehending their separate and combined effects on glycemic management is the study's primary goal.¹

Comorbidities like hypertension, dyslipidemia, and cardiovascular diseases make managing type 2 diabetes even more difficult and require the use of several medications. Concurrent use of five or more medications is known as polypharmacy, and it is frequently seen in diabetic patients. Because of the increased complexity, pill burden, and potential for drug-drug interactions, polypharmacy can negatively impact adherence.^{8,9} Therefore, evaluating the effects of polypharmacy on medication adherence in T2DM patients is the second goal.

One of the most important aspects of managing diabetes is taking **medications** as prescribed. Inadequate compliance with insulin or oral hypoglycemia medication regimens leads to long-term complications, higher hospitalisation rates, and less than ideal glycemic control. On the other hand, low HbA1c levels and lower medical expenses are linked to good adherence.⁷ Therefore, evaluating the impact of medication adherence on the quality of life of people with type 2 diabetes is the third goal of this research.

The ultimate goal of this study is to enhance the general **quality of life (QoL)** of individuals with type 2 diabetes. Mental, emotional, and social well-being all have an impact on quality of life in addition to physical health. There is a significant psychosocial burden associated with having diabetes, and enhancing quality of life necessitates addressing elements like education, treatment satisfaction, lifestyle modification, and psychological support.^{10,11} This study attempts to offer thorough insights for interventions that improve long-term outcomes and the lived experience of individuals with type 2 diabetes by examining the interactions among glycemic control, adherence, and polypharmacy.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD:

2.1 Study design:

Prospective observational study

2.2 Study Period:

The study was conducted over a period of 06 months.

2.3 Study site:

Department of Internal Medicine – Sagar Hospitals, Jayanagar, Bengaluru.

2.4 Study Criteria:

2.4.1 Inclusion criteria:

All type 2 diabetes mellitus patient with the age of 18 years and above at least 4 months duration following the initial diagnosis, All subjects with co-morbid condition, The patients who had a recent laboratory report on the glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) level

2.4.2 Exclusion criteria:

- Gestational diabetic patient
- Patient with diabetes retinopathy
- Patient with cognitive impairment

2.5 Sample Size Calculation:

Procedure for sample size calculation: Involves two steps

Step 1: Calculation of sample size for infinite population

Step 2: Calculation for required population

❖ For infinite population

$$\text{Formula: } ss = \frac{Z^2 \times P \times (1-P)}{W^2}$$

ss – Sample size for infinite population

Z – 1.96 for 95% of confidence level

P – Prevalence = 10.5% (0.105)

W- Degree of accuracy required = 0.05

1-P – Incidence

After substitution, from the above formula, we get 161

Therefore, the sample size for infinite population (ss) is 161.

❖ **So, sample size for finite population:**

$$\text{Corrected SS} = \frac{\text{ss}}{\frac{1 + [\text{ss} - 1]}{\text{Pop}}}$$

pop = your survey's target population 720

Here, after substituting ss and pop values we get 131,

Therefore, the corrected/adjusted value to the required population is 131.

2.6 METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA/STUDY PROCEDURE:

Method:

[IRB approval date 16-03-2024]

A prospective observational study was conducted for six months in the Internal Medicine Department of Sagar Hospitals Jayanagar-Bengaluru. All type 2 diabetes mellitus patients aged 18 years and above with a disease duration of at least 4 months after initial diagnosis, including those with co-morbid conditions, and who had a recent laboratory report on glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels were included in the study. Exclusion criteria include Patients with specific conditions, including gestational diabetes, diabetic retinopathy, and cognitive impairment, to focus on a defined population.

Consent was taken from all the patients included in the study for publication of the collected information.

Data was collected from the patient's case note, laboratory reports, treatment chart and patient interaction. Our study also aimed educating patient's/patient's attender about the disease and the treatment by providing them with leaflets that includes complete information about what is type 2 diabetes mellitus, signs and symptoms, complications, management which enhances patient knowledge about the disease and the treatment. The leaflet was validated by expert panel members [Doctor's and Chief Dietician of Sagar Hospitals] both Kannada and English version.

- Design validity was done using BALD criteria.
- Content validity using Lawshe's content validity ratio.
- Readability validity using Flesch's Reading Ease Score and Flesch-Kincaid Readability Test

PROCESS OF CONDUCT

2.6.1 Statistical method

Statistical analysis has been carried out in the present study. Chi-square test was defined at a 5% level of significance, i.e., p-value <0.05. The results were shown as percentages and proportions for categorical variables. Google Forms are used to gather data.

2.6.2 Statistical software

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software for data input and analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Demographics:

The study was conducted on 248 T2DM Patients among them 115 are male and 133 are female and provided a 100% response rate.

Table no 01: Subject Distribution based on the gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	115	46.4
Female	133	53.6
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, 46.4% (115) were male, 53.6% (133) were female. This indicates a slightly higher proportion of female participants compared to males.

Table No 2: Distribution of the subjects based on the age

Age group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
30 – 45 years	33	13.3
46 – 59 years	80	32.3
More than 60 years	135	54.4
Total	248	100

The age distribution shows that 54.4% (135) are over 60 years old, while for 32.3% (80) were between 46 to 59 years old, and 13.3% of participants are between 30 and 45 years. The data reflects a predominance of older adults in the study

Table no 3: Distribution of the subjects based on the physical inactivity barrier

Physical inactivity	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	31	12.5
Yes	217	87.5
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, 87.5% (217) individuals are physically inactive while only 12.5% (31) participants are physically active. This indicates significant need for increased physical exercise among this group.

Table no 4: Distribution of the subjects based on the poor diet barrier

Poor diet	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	98	39.5
Yes	150	60.5
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, 60.5% (150) of participants having a poor diet, while 39.5% (98) individuals follow a healthier diet.

Table no 5: Distribution of the subjects based on the inconsistent blood glucose barrier

IBGM	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	92	37.1
Yes	156	62.9
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, 62.9% (156) participants have Inconsistent blood glucose monitoring while only 37.1% (92) have consistent blood glucose monitoring.

Table no 06: Distribution of the subjects based on the medication – fear of side effects barrier

Fear of side effects	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	206	83.1
Yes	42	16.9
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, majority of patients 83.1% (206) do not have fear side effects, while only 16.9% (42) have fear of side effects.

Table no 7: Distribution of the subjects based on the co-morbid disease barrier

Comorbidity	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	26	10.5
Yes	222	89.5
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, 89.5% (222) individuals having comorbid conditions, while only 10.5% (26) individuals do not have co-morbid disease.

Table no 8: Distribution of the subjects based on the emotional status – stress barrier

Type of stress	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Family stress	157	63.4
Occupational stress	39	15.7
Financial stress	52	20.9
Total	248	100

Among 248 participants, 63.3% (157) have family stress, while 15.7% (39) have occupational stress, while 20.96% (52) have financial stress.

Table no 09: Distribution of the subjects based on HbA1c level

HbA1c	Diabetes	Baseline		Follow – up	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
≤ 7%	Good	41	16.5	54	21.7
7.1 – 7.9%	Fair	66	26.6	95	38.4
> 8.0%	Poor	141	56.9	99	39.9
Total		248	100	248	100
Chi-square statistic = 14.352, p-value<0.001 (significant association)					

The table no 9 shows HbA1c levels of participants at baseline and follow-up. At baseline, 16.5% (41) had good control, 26.6% (66) had fair control, and 56.9% (141) had poor control. By the follow-up, good control increased to 21.7% (54), fair control rose to 38.4% (95), and poor control decreased to 39.9% (99), indicating an overall improvement in diabetes management.

Table no 10: Distribution of subjects based on FBS Levels

FBS (mg/dL)	Baseline		Follow – up	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
80 – 130	51	20.5	64	25.8
130 – 160	76	30.6	96	38.7
> 160	121	48.9	88	35.5
Total	248	100	248	100
Chi-square statistic = 9.005, p-value 0.011 (significant association)				

The table no 10 shows fasting blood sugar (FBS) levels of participants at baseline and follow-up. At baseline, 20.5% (51) had FBS between 80–130, 30.6% (76) had FBS between 130–160, and 48.9% (121) had FBS above 160. By the follow-up, the percentage of participants with FBS between 80–130 increased to 25.8% (64), those with FBS between 130–160 rose to 38.7% (96), and those with FBS above 160 decreased to 35.5% (88). This suggests improved FBS levels over the time.

Table no 11: Distribution of subjects based on PPBS Levels

PPBS (mg/dL)	Baseline		Follow – up	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 180	48	19.3	61	24.5
180 – 200	73	29.4	96	38.8
> 200	127	51.2	91	36.7
Total	248	100	248	100
Chi-square statistic = 10.625, p-value 0.004 (significant association)				

The table no 11 shows postprandial blood sugar (PPBS) levels at baseline and follow-up. At baseline, 19.3% (48) had PPBS levels below 180, 29.4% (73) had levels between 180–200, and 51.2% (127) had levels above 200. By the follow-up, participants with PPBS levels below 180 increased to 24.5% (61), those between 180–200 rose to 38.8% (96), and those with levels above 200 decreased to 36.7% (91). This indicates an overall improvement in PPBS levels over time.

Table no 12: Distribution of the subjects based on presence of barriers and their HbA1c status

Barriers	Good < 7%	Fair 7 – 7.9%	Poor ≥ 8%	Yes n
A) Physical inactivity	22	71	124	217
	10.1	32.7	57.2	100%
B) Poor diet	24	40	86	150
	16	26.6	57.3	100%
C) IGBM	42	47	67	156
	26.9	30.2	42.9	100%
D) Medication – Fear of side effects	6	11	25	42
	11.9	23.8	61.9	100%
E) Co morbidity	16	90	116	222
	7.3	40.5	52.2	100%
F) Family stress	25	42	90	157
	19.1	26.7	54.2	100
G) Occupational stress	5	12	22	39
	17.9	25.6	56.5	100
H) Financial stress	8	14	30	52
	15.3	26.9	57.6	100%

The table no 12 A, B, C highlights the barriers to achieving good, fair, and poor glycemic control (HbA1c levels) based on physical inactivity, poor diet, and inadequate glucose monitoring behaviour (IGBM). Among those with physical inactivity, 10.1% (22) had good control, 32.7% (71) had fair control, and 57.2% (124) had poor control. For those with a poor diet, 16% (24) had good control, 26.6% (40) had fair control, and 57.3% (86) had poor control. Among those with IGBM, 26.9% (42) had good control, 30.2% (47) had fair control, and 42.9% (67) had poor control. This suggests that physical inactivity and poor diet are more strongly associated with poor glycemic control compared to IGBM.

The table no 12 D, E highlights the impact of two barriers—fear of medication side effects and comorbidities—on glycemic control. Among participants with fear of medication side effects, 11.9% (6) had good control, 23.8% (11) had fair control, and 61.9% (25) had poor control. For those with comorbidities, 7.3% (16) had good control, 40.5% (90) had fair control, and 52.2% (116) had poor control. This indicates that both barriers, particularly comorbidities, are associated with poorer glycemic control.

The table 12 F, G, H illustrates the effect of family, occupational, and financial stress on glycemic control. Among participants with family stress, 19.1% (25) had good control, 26.7% (42) had fair control, and 54.2% (90) had poor control. For those with occupational stress, 17.9% (5) had good control, 25.6% (12) had fair control, and 56.5% (22) had poor control. Among those experiencing financial stress, 15.3% (8) had good control, 26.9% (14) had fair control, and 57.6% (30) had poor control. Overall, all three stress factors are associated with a higher percentage of poor glycemic control.

Table no 13: Distribution of the subjects based on the presence of co-morbidities

Co-morbid diseases	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Hypertension	235	94.8
Hypothyroidism	90	36.3
Osteoporosis	54	21.8
Chronic kidney disease (CKD)	48	19.4
Myocardial Infarction (MI)	48	19.4
Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD)	45	18.1
Dyslipidaemia	28	11.3
Peripheral neuropathy	11	4.4
Bronchial asthma	10	4.0

The table no 13 presents the prevalence of comorbid diseases among participants. Hypertension is the most common comorbidity, affecting 94.8% (235). Hypothyroidism is present in 36.3% (90), while osteoporosis affects 21.8% (54). Chronic kidney disease (CKD) and myocardial infarction (MI) each affect 19.4% (48). Ischemic heart disease (IHD) occurs in 18.1% (45), dyslipidaemia in 11.3% (28), peripheral neuropathy in 4.4% (11), and bronchial asthma in 4.0% (10). Hypertension is overwhelmingly the most prevalent comorbid disease.

Table no 14: Distribution of the subjects based on the total number of medications

No of medications	Frequency	Percentage (%)
2	27	10.9
3	91	36.7
4	15	6.0
5	9	3.6
6	14	5.6
7	47	19.0
8	41	16.5
9	3	1.2
10	1	0.4
Total	248	100

The table no 14 presents distribution of the number of medications taken by participants. The majority, 36.7% (91) take 3 medications, followed by 19.0% (47) taking 7 medications, and 16.5% (41) taking 8 medications. A smaller percentage, 10.9% (27), take 2 medications, while 6.0% (15) take 4 medications. Additionally, 5.6% (14) are on 6 medications, and only 1.2% (3) take 9 medications, with the lowest percentage, 0.4% (1), taking 10 medications. This data highlights that most participants are on 3 medications, with fewer on higher or lower medication regimens.

Table no 15: Distribution of the subjects based on the presence of poly pharmacy

Polypharmacy	Frequency	Percent
Nil	132	53.2
Yes	116	46.8
Total	248	100

The table no 15 highlights the prevalence of polypharmacy among participants. A little over half, 53.2% (132), are not on polypharmacy, while 46.8% (116) are taking multiple medications. This indicates that nearly half of the participants experience polypharmacy, which can be a concern in managing chronic conditions.

Table no 16: Comparison of polypharmacy subjects with their medication adherence status

	HILL-BONE MEDICATION ADHERENCE SCORE			TOTAL
	< 18 (Low Adherence)	18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	> 27 (High Adherence)	
POLYPHARMACY	43	56	17	116
	37.0	48.3	14.7	100.0%

The table no 16 presents the relationship between polypharmacy and medication adherence according to the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Score. Among participants with polypharmacy, 37.0% (43) had low adherence (<18), 48.3% (56) had moderate adherence (18–27), and 14.7% (17) had high adherence (>27). This suggests that a significant proportion of participants on polypharmacy tend to have low or moderate adherence, with fewer achieving high adherence.

Table no 17: Distribution of subjects based on Hill Bone Medication Adherence Scores

HILL BONE MEDICATION ADHERENCE SCORE	BASELINE		FOLLOW UP	
	FREQUEN CY	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUEN CY	PERCENTAGE (%)
< 18 (Low Adherence)	92	37.0	05	2.01
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	105	42.3	135	54.4
> 27 (High Adherence)	51	20.7	108	43.5
TOTAL	248	100.0	248	100.0
Chi-square statistic = 102.214, p-value <0.001 (significant association)				

The table no 17 and graph outlines changes in medication adherence as measured by the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Score from baseline to follow-up. At baseline, 37.0% (92) exhibited low adherence, 42.3% (105) had moderate adherence, and 20.7% (51) demonstrated high adherence. By the follow-up, there was a significant improvement in adherence: low adherence decreased to 2.01% (5), while moderate adherence increased to 54.4% (135) and high adherence rose to 43.5% (108). These results indicate a positive shift in medication adherence among participants over time.

Table no 18: Hill Bone Medication Adherence Scores at baseline in male and female

BASELINE HBMAS SCORE	GENDER		Total
	Male	Female	
< 18 (Low Adherence)	64	28	92
	25.8	11.2	37.0%
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	40	65	105
	16.1	26.4	42.2%
> 27 (High Adherence)	11	40	51
	4.4	16.1	20.5%
TOTAL	115	133	248
	46.3	53.7	100%
Chi-square statistic = 35.409, p-value <0.001 (significant association)			

The table no 18 and graph presents the baseline medication adherence scores based on gender, as measured by the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Scale (HBMAS). Among males, 25.8% (64) were categorized as having low adherence (<18), while 16.1% males (40) fell into the moderate adherence category (18–27), and 4.4% males (11) exhibited high adherence (>27). In contrast, females demonstrated a different adherence pattern: 11.2% females (28) had low adherence, 26.4%(65) had moderate adherence, and 16.1% (40) showed high adherence. This data indicates that a larger proportion of males had low adherence compared to females, whereas females had a higher percentage of moderate and high adherence.

Table no 19: Hill Bone Medication Adherence Scores at follow up in male and female

Follow Up HBMAS SCORE	GENDER		Total
	Male	Female	
< 18 (Low Adherence)	3	2	05
	1.2	0.8	2.01
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	62	73	135
	25	29.4	54.4
> 27 (High Adherence)	50	58	108
	20.2	23.3	43.5
TOTAL	115	133	248
	46.4	53.6	100%
Chi-square statistic = 0.384, p-value 0.825 (no significant association)			

The table 19 and graph display follow-up medication adherence scores by gender, using the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Scale (HBMAS). At follow-up, 1.2% (3 males) and 0.8% (2 females) were classified as having low adherence (<18), showing a significant reduction from baseline. In the moderate adherence category (18–27), 25% (62 males) and 29.4% (73 females) improved, with females having a slightly higher percentage. In the high adherence category (>27), 20.2% (50 males) and 23.3% (58 females) demonstrated adherence, reflecting notable increases for both genders. Overall, both males and females showed improvements in adherence, with females consistently exhibiting higher percentages in the moderate and high categories.

Table no 20: Hill Bone Medication Adherence scores at baseline in different age

BASELINE HBMAS SCORE	AGE INTERVAL			Total
	30 – 35	46 – 59	> 60	
< 18 (Low Adherence)	8	21	63	92
	3.2	8.4	25.4	37.0
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	15	43	47	105
	6.0	17.3	18.9	42.2%
> 27 (High Adherence)	10	16	25	51
	4.0	6.4	10.0	20.5%
TOTAL	33	80	135	248
	13.3	32.3	54.4	100%

Chi-square statistic = 13.490, p-value 0.009 (significant association)

The table show baseline medication adherence scores by age intervals according to the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Scale (HBMAS). In the low adherence category (<18), 3.2% (8) are aged 30–35, 8.4% (21) are 46–59, and 25.4% (63) are over 60, totalling 37.0% (92). For moderate adherence (18–27), 6.0% (15) are 30–35, 17.3% (43) are 46–59, and 18.9% (47) are over 60, making up 42.2% (105). In the high adherence category (>27), 4.0% (10) are 30–35, 6.4% (16) are 46–59, and 10.0% (25) are over 60, totalling 20.5% (51). The data shows that most participants with low adherence are older, while moderate and high adherence is more evenly distributed across age groups.

Table no 21: Hill Bone Medication Adherence scores at follow up in different age group

FOLLOW UP HBMAS SCORE	AGE INTERVAL			Total
	30 – 35	47 – 59	> 60	
< 18 (Low Adherence)	0	2	3	5
	0	0.80	1.2	2.01
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	10	41	84	135
	4.0	16.5	33.8	54.4
> 27 (High Adherence)	23	37	48	108
	9.2	14.9	19.3	43.5
TOTAL	33	80	135	248
	13.3	32.3	54.4	100%
Cannot be estimated due to zero count.				

The table no 21 shows follow-up medication adherence scores by age intervals based on the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Scale (HBMAS). In the low adherence category (<18), 0% (0) are aged 30–35, 0.8% (2) are aged 46–59, and 1.2% (3) are over 60, totalling 2.01% (5). For moderate adherence (18–27), 4.0% (10) are 30–35, 16.5% (41) are 46–59, and 33.8% (84) are over 60, accounting for 54.4% (n=135). In the high adherence category (>27), 9.2% (23) are 30–35, 14.9% (37) are 46–59, and 19.3% (48) are over 60, totalling 43.5% (108). Overall, there is a notable improvement in adherence scores, especially among older participants in the moderate and high categories.

Table no 22: Distribution of subjects based on RV – DQOL Scores

RV – DIABETES QUALITY OF LIFE SCORES	BASELINE		FOLLOW UP	
	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
40 – 65 (Poor)	138	55.6	9	3.7
27 – 39 (Moderate)	72	29.0	126	50.8
13 – 26 (Good)	38	15.4	113	45.5
TOTAL	248	100.0	248	100.0
Chi-square statistic = 165.183, p-value <0.001 (significant association)				

The table compares baseline and follow-up diabetes quality of life scores. At baseline, 55.6% reported poor quality (40–65), which decreased to 3.7% at follow-up. Moderate quality (27–39) increased from 29.0% to 50.8%, while good quality (13–26) rose from 15.4% to 45.5%. These results indicate significant improvement in quality of life over time.

Table no 23: RV – DQOL Scores at baseline in male and female

RV – DIABETES QUALITY OF LIFE SCORES	GENDER		Total
	Male	Female	
40 – 65 (Poor)	71	67	138
	28.6	27.0	55.6
27 – 39 (Moderate)	31	41	72
	12.5	16.5	29.0
13 – 26 (Good)	13	25	38
	5.2	10.0	15.4
	115	133	248
	46.3	53.7	100%
Chi-square statistic = 4.009, p-value 0.134 (no significant association)			

The table 23 compares baseline and follow-up diabetes quality of life scores. At baseline, 55.6% (138 participants) reported poor quality of life (40–65), but this dropped significantly to 3.7% (9 participants) at follow-up. The percentage of participants with moderate quality of life (27–39) increased from 29.0% (72 participants) at baseline to 50.8% (126 participants) at follow-up. Similarly, those reporting good quality of life (13–26) rose from 15.4% (38 participants) at baseline to 45.5% (113 participants) at follow-up. These results indicate a substantial improvement in quality of life over time.

Table no 24: RV – DQOL Scores at follow up in male and female

RV - DIABETES QUALITY OF LIFE SCORES	GENDER		Total
	Male	Female	
40 – 65	5	4	9
(Poor)	2.0	1.6	3.6
27 – 39	58	68	126
(Moderate)	23.3	27.4	50.8
13 – 26	52	61	113
(Good)	20.9	24.5	45.5
	115	133	248
	46.3	53.7	100%
Chi-square statistic = 0.3168, p-value 0.853 (no significant association)			

The table 24 categorizes diabetes quality of life scores by gender. For poor quality (40–65), 2.0% of males and 1.6% of females reported low quality of life. In the moderate category (27–39), 23.3% of males and 27.4% of females indicated moderate quality. For good quality (13–26), 20.9% of males and 24.5% of females had high quality of life. Overall, more females fall into the moderate and good quality of life categories compared to males.

Table No 25: Effect of Medication Adherence scores at Baseline on RV- DQOL baseline

BASELINE HBMAS SCORE	BASELINE RV – DQOL Scores			Total
	40 – 45 (Poor)	27 – 39 (Moderate)	13 – 26 (Good)	
< 18 (Low Adherence)	35	40	17	92
	14.1	16.1	6.8	37.2
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	43	38	24	105
	17.3	15.3	9.6	42.3
> 27 (High Adherence)	7	11	33	51
	2.8	4.4	13.3	20.5
	85	89	74	248
	34.3	35.8	29.9	100%

Chi-square statistic = 38.897, p-value < 0.001 (significant association)

The table 25 shows the relationship between baseline medication adherence and diabetes quality of life. In the low adherence group (<18), 14.1% reported poor quality, 16.1% had moderate quality, and 6.8% had good quality, totalling 37.2%. For moderate adherence (18–27), 17.3% experienced poor quality, 15.3% had moderate quality, and 9.6% had good quality, making up 42.3%. In the high adherence group (>27), 2.8% reported poor quality, 4.4% had moderate quality, and 13.3% had good quality, totalling 20.5%. This indicates better quality of life with higher adherence.

**Table No 26: Effect of Medication Adherence scores at Follow up on RV- DQOL
Follow up**

Follow Up HBMAS SCORE	Follow Up RV – DQOL Scores			Total
	40 – 45 (Poor)	27 – 39 (Moderate)	13 – 26 (Good)	
< 18 (Low Adherence)	0	2	3	5
	0	0.80	1.2	2.0%
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	20	50	65	135
	8.0	20.1	26.2	54.4%
> 27 (High Adherence)	6	20	82	108
	2.41	8.0	33.0	43.5%
TOTAL	26	72	150	248
	10.5	29.0	60.5	100%
Cannot be estimated due to 0 count				

The table no 26 shows the relationship between medication adherence and diabetes quality of life. In the low adherence group (<18), 0% had poor quality of life, 0.8% had moderate quality, and 1.2% reported good quality, totalling 2.0%. For moderate adherence (18–27), 8.0% had poor quality, 20.1% had moderate quality, and 26.2% had good quality, making up 54.4%. In the high adherence group (>27), 2.41% had poor quality, 8.0% had moderate quality, and 33.0% had good quality, totalling 43.5%. This shows improved quality of life with higher adherence levels.

Table no. 27: Improvement in the overall quality of life of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients

HbA1c (%) Improvement					
HbA1c	Diabetes	Baseline		Follow – up	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
$\leq 7\%$	Good	41	16.5	54	21.7
7.1 – 7.9%	Fair	66	26.6	95	38.4
$> 8.0\%$	Poor	141	56.9	99	39.9
Total		248	100	248	100
Chi-square statistic = 14.352, p-value<0.001 (significant association)					

Hill bone Medication adherence score improvements (HBMAS)				
HILL BONE MEDICATION ADHERENCE SCORE	BASELINE		FOLLOW UP	
	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
< 18 (Low Adherence)	92	37.0	05	2.01
18 – 27 (Moderate Adherence)	105	42.3	135	54.4
> 27 (High Adherence)	51	20.7	108	43.5
TOTAL	248	100.0	248	100.0
Chi-square statistic = 102.214, p-value <0.001 (significant association)				

RV- Diabetes quality of life improvements (RV – DQOL)				
RV – DIABETES QUALITY OF LIFE SCORES	BASELINE		FOLLOW UP	
	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
40 – 65 (Poor)	138	55.6	9	3.7
27 – 39 (Moderate)	72	29.0	126	50.8
13 – 26 (Good)	38	15.4	113	45.5
TOTAL	248	100.0	248	100.0
Chi-square statistic = 165.183, p-value <0.001 (significant association)				

Figure no. 01: Improvement in the overall quality of life of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients

The table no. 27 and graph present the comprehensive type 2 diabetes management among 248 participants. Significant improvements were observed in HbA1c levels, medication adherence, and quality of life. At baseline, a majority of patients (56.9%) exhibited poor glycemic control (HbA1c > 8%), but this reduced to 39.9% at follow-up, with a corresponding increase in the proportion of patients with good control (≤ 7%). Medication adherence improved drastically, as low adherence (Hill Bone score < 18) decreased from 37% to 2.01%, while high adherence (> 27) more than doubled, rising from 20.7% to 43.5%. Quality of life also showed remarkable enhancement, with the proportion of patients reporting poor scores (40-65) dropping from 55.6% to 3.7%, while those with good scores (13-26) increased significantly from 15.4% to 45.5%. The results, supported by highly significant chi-square statistics (p-value < 0.001), highlight the effectiveness of the intervention in improving clinical outcomes and overall patient well-being.

CONCLUSION:

This study titled ‘A comprehensive study on type 2 diabetes mellitus : exploring and addressing the barriers and facilitators’ provides an in-depth analysis of the multifaceted challenges faced by individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) in managing their condition. The study utilized a combination of socio-demographic analysis, clinical data, and self-reported measures, including the Hill-Bone Medication Adherence Score (HBMAS) and RV – Diabetes Quality of Life (DQOL) Scores, to assess medication adherence, glycemic control, and quality of life, particularly regarding medication adherence, glycemic control, and quality of life. The research identifies significant barriers such as physical inactivity, poor diet, inconsistent blood glucose monitoring, and the presence of co-morbid conditions, all of which complicate effective diabetes management. Emotional stress, particularly family-related stress, emerges as a key factor influencing adherence, while polypharmacy adds further complexity to treatment regimens. Despite these challenges, the study shows that tailored interventions can significantly improve both medication adherence and quality of life, with notable improvements observed in adherence levels and quality of life scores over time. Older adults and females, in particular, demonstrate positive outcomes with higher adherence rates and better perceived quality of life. The PIL, along with patient education strategies, proved effective in promoting medication compliance and success. The findings underscore the need for comprehensive, patient-centered strategies that address emotional, physical, and medical barriers to improve health outcomes for patients managing T2DM. Overall findings suggest that addressing the multi- dimensional barriers lead to improved health outcomes and better patient experiences.

Conflict of interest statement

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript, and there is no conflict of interest as agreed upon in the content of this research.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical committee clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Sagar Hospitals, Jayanagar, Bengaluru.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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